

Towards the Embodiment of Active Sensing in Robotic Systems

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Abstract—Active sensing enables robots to interact dynamically with their environment by optimizing sensory information flow. However, replicating this in robotic systems poses challenges, particularly in developing metrics that account for sensor limitations and actuation noise, as well as integrating active sensing into control architectures. This paper presents an overview of active sensing integration, explaining a metric based on the Constructibility and Reachability Gramians and showing a methodology for incorporating active sensing into task-oriented control using a modified Lyapunov-based Model Predictive Control framework. The approach is validated through simulations on a unicycle vehicle.

I. INTRODUCTION

Delving into the complexities of active sensing uncovers its essential role in our cognitive processes, involving perception, where sensory data is processed, and action, where we minimize noises affecting sensory information [1]. In planning the actions, the brain uses active sensing strategies to integrate sensory data with prior experience, enhancing environmental understanding [2]. This concept has widely influenced robotics, where active sensing is seen as an action selection process that maximizes the amount of sensory information. This process is crucial for estimating unknown robot positions or environmental parameters, directly influencing the execution of assigned tasks [3]. Replicating this in robots presents two main challenges: *i*) identifying appropriate metrics for quantifying sensory information flow, as action selection highly depends on the chosen metric; and *ii*) integrating active sensing into robots by incorporating information measures within the task-control architecture.

Information metrics have been widely explored in robotics [4], [5]. However, these approaches consider always available noisy measurements, neglecting sensor limitations and the degrading effects of actuation noise. Metrics based on the Estimation Covariance Matrix [6], which consider intermittent measurements and actuation/process noise, are limited to employing the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) as an observer.

As previously mentioned, action selection complements perception and is a fundamental aspect of efficient motion planning, focusing on selecting the actions to enhance a robot's perceptive capabilities, thereby improving estimation performance [7]. However, robotic functionality extends

beyond accuracy in estimations. Robots perform tasks influenced by the acquired information, which significantly impacts the effectiveness and efficiency of task execution. The integration of perception and task execution remains a challenging problem in the literature, often addressed by selecting actions that minimize the uncertainty in task actions [8] or through hierarchical approaches [9]. However, these approaches frequently neglect the issue of stability in their formulations.

This paper shows an active sensing metric that accounts for sensor limitations and actuation noise to address these limitations. Additionally, it presents a methodology for integrating active sensing into a task-oriented control scheme, ensuring stability throughout the task execution.

II. FROM MAXIMIZING INFORMATION TO ENHANCING TASK EXECUTION

This section explains a solution for replicating active perception in robotic systems, describing an active sensing metric (Sec. II-A) and a methodology for integrating active sensing in robotic systems (Sec. II-B). For more details, see [10], [11], respectively.

A. Measuring information flow through combinations of the Constructibility and Reachability Gramians

The first challenge in implementing active sensing in robots is identifying suitable metrics to quantify sensory information flow, i.e., the information gained through sensors and the one lost due to the degrading effect of actuation noise. This section provides an effective active sensing metric based on combinations of the smallest eigenvalue of the Constructibility Gramian (CG) and Reachability Gramian (RG). This combination enables the design of a novel metric that, unlike existing approaches in the literature, quantifies the sensory information gathered along a trajectory while accounting for the degrading effects of actuation noise.

In [5], a norm of the CG was used to quantify the collected information, assuming negligible actuation/process noise. In contrast, [10] proposes the RG to quantify the impact of actuation/process noise on sensory information. Since measurement and actuation noises simultaneously affect a robotic system, combining both Gramians is expected to improve the state estimation performance. Based on the discussion above, we identified an information-aware cost function as a weighted sum of the smallest eigenvalues of the Gramians. The cost function J_1 uses the smallest eigenvalue of the RG projected onto the CG's null space, directing the degrading effects of actuation/process noise toward the less uncertain direction in the unobservable space, where sensor information is useless, allowing the information content in the observable space to maximize freely. The cost function is maximized within an optimal control problem and compared

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Fig. 1. Minimum amount of information ($\lambda_{\min}(\mathbf{P}^{-1}(t))$), along the planned trajectory. At t_f , $\lambda_{\min}(\mathbf{P}_f^{-1})$ is 2.1 for J_1 and 1.15 for CG.

to the CG-based approach from [5]. When actuation noise is neglected, the CG aligns with the Fisher Information Matrix, which is used as a state-of-the-art baseline. The comparison involves a simulated unicycle with an omnidirectional FoV sensor, limited to 5 m range, using an EKF for position estimation while reaching a target configuration, $\mathbf{q}(t_f) = \mathbf{q}_f$. Measurement noise follows a Gaussian distribution, while actuation noise uses a more degrading Brownian distribution. Fig. 1 shows the minimum amount of information along the planned trajectories. The J_1 -based optimal trajectory achieves \mathbf{q}_f with the lowest estimation uncertainty, indicating J_1 as the most effective active sensing metric in the presence of intermittent measurements and actuation noise. As discussed in [5], [10], a significant challenge in implementing active sensing strategies is the computation of the system's state transition matrix. This complexity escalates with more complex robotic systems. To mitigate this challenge, in [12], we proposed a solution utilizing feedback linearization to reduce the computational load of an active sensing algorithm, and we successfully tested it on a simulated planar quadrotor.

B. A Lyapunov-based MPC architecture for ensuring high-quality perception and proved stability in task execution

After selecting the active sensing metric, it needs to be integrated into a task-oriented control scheme to enhance both estimation performance and task execution. Our solution in aligning perception and task execution while ensuring stability is the Lyapunov-based Model Predictive Control (LMPC) scheme, which we have modified within a feedback-feedforward framework (see Fig. 2(a)), where the feedforward component maximizes the smallest eigenvalue of the CG, and the feedback component ensures the stability of the desired task in the Lyapunov sense. This architecture is termed Information-aware LMPC (ILMPC). To evaluate the effectiveness of our approach, we tested it on a unicycle vehicle performing a path-following task equipped with a range sensor measuring the distance from the path $h(t) = y(t)$ and employing an EKF for recovering its position. Gaussian output noise is assumed, with negligible actuation/process noise. We conducted 100 simulations, comparing the ILMPC with a Lyapunov Control Law (LCL) that considers only feedback action, and a standard LMPC using a task-oriented cost function. Fig. 2(b) presents the mean and standard deviation of the task errors. ILMPC is the only approach that ensures accurate task execution, with bounded errors. In conclusion, ILMPC represents an effective alternative for incorporating active sensing into a task-oriented control scheme while maintaining stability throughout the motion.

(a) LMPC framework.

(b) Task error comparison.

Fig. 2. LMPC for aligning perception to task execution.

III. FUTURE WORKS

Future work will involve testing the ILMPC framework under conditions of intermittent measurements and actuation noise and performing real-world experiments to validate its effectiveness. Additionally, we are working on extending our approach to obstacle avoidance, by also handling estimation errors throughout the whole trajectory.

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